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Unveiling the Narratives of Seasoned Reading Coordinators: A Phenomenological Investigation

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers. This study engaged qualitative method, utilizing phenomenological approach. The participants of the study were 14 reading coordinators from Municipality of Kapalong Davao del Norte teaching a struggling reader. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Through thematic analysis, patterns and common themes that emerged from the participants' experiences were identified and grouped. This allowed for the extraction of core themes related to the challenges and strategies employed by reading coordinators. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: facing difficulties due students' difficulty in developing fundamental literacy skills, lack of parental support, difficulty to comprehend, and struggle in aligning strategies with students reading ability, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: cultivating a supportive environment for struggling readers, be consistent in teaching the struggling readers, maintaining positive reinforcement and motivation in teaching, fostering collaboration and community engagement in reading programs. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: patience and empathy in teaching struggling readers, innovative teaching strategies and adaptability in addressing struggling readers, essence of differentiated instruction for diverse learners and gaining a sense of fulfillment from teaching. The results of this study were deemed significant by the participants, teachers, students and researchers.

Keywords: *experiences, seasoned reading coordinators, struggling readers, thematic analysis, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

Reading is a fundamental skill that students begin to learn early in their education. However, the process of teaching children to read is quite challenging, especially to the side of the teacher. Reading coordinators experience several challenges regarding teaching students to read including, time constraints, insufficient manpower, lack of training and knowledge, and limited resources. In addition, even if a teacher could teach reading, it will be difficult for them to do effectively if the appropriate textbooks are not available. Due to the lack of staff, teachers are become overworked and must attend many classes. As a result, they would not be able to give attention to the students who struggle with reading (Stanton, 2021).

As a matter of fact, in the context of the international setting particularly in Nigeria, teachers have been working under difficult circumstances, as too many students in a class and poor student attendance among others are issues in Nigerian elementary schools. Furthermore, the shortage of teaching and learning materials is a challenge to teaching reading skills to Nigerian students. Teachers encounter several challenges when teaching reading. These include students' limited background and foundational knowledge in English language studies, a lack of motivation toward learning English in general and reading skills in particular, overcrowded classrooms, and insufficient library resources. Even though they encounter obstacles like low salaries, insufficient recognition, and limited resources, these educators persist in positively impacting their students' lives (KIR, 2023).

Meanwhile in the Philippines, teaching reading is a priority that the government is actively investing time and resources into to improve overall literacy levels. In this context, teachers are expected to employ a range of varied, relevant, and effective methodologies and strategies to develop students' reading skills. The challenges teachers encounter while educating students are exacerbated by a lack of advanced reading resources (Maffea, 2020). Additionally, teachers struggle when students fail to understand the material due to their reluctance to read. Consequently, a teacher's patience can be challenged when teaching struggling readers, as it requires them to manage difficult or unsatisfactory circumstances and delayed results with composure. (Wu et al., 2021).

This study has social relevance because studying the experiences of seasoned reading coordinators provides insight into the experiences and perspectives of reading coordinators. This can contribute to the understanding of effective reading coordination, educational practices, and professional development in the context of literacy education. This study will also benefit the following person and agencies like schools will benefit from this study because it will give them precise facts on how to support struggling readers. Educators serve as a vital support system for students. On the other hand, this study highlights the urgent need for research because teaching students with reading difficulties is critical. The consequences of low reading proficiency can be severe; students who do not learn to read effectively are more likely to experience widespread academic challenges and face a higher risk of dropping out of school. Therefore, this problem needs to be addressed immediately.

In connection, related studies had been found regarding the phenomenon of the experiences of seasoned reading coordinators entitled: "Helping Struggling Readers to Read: The Impact of the Care for the Non-Readers (CRN) Program on Filipino Pupils' Reading Proficiency" by Mangila and Adapon (2020). Their study sought to evaluate how the non-reader care program affects the reading

performance of struggling readers in elementary schools. Also, the study by Walker (2020) entitled:

“The Experiences of Teachers Successfully Teaching Reading to Black Students” investigated the challenges faced by the teachers of non-readers. However, the distinctive aspect of the current study primarily centers on the experiences of experienced reading coordinators as they address the needs of non-readers, a topic that has been less explored in other research to date. Through this exploration, I endeavor to amplify the voices of reading coordinators, recognize their efforts, and ultimately cover the way for more inclusive and supportive educational environments for students with reading difficulties.

Upon the completion of this study, dissemination efforts would be done to encourage the readers and members of the academy community to disseminate further and utilize the findings of this study. A free copy of the study would be given to the school where the study would be conducted. Furthermore, I would guarantee the publication of this study in a reputable and refereed journal to encourage further dissemination of this study.

Research Questions

In order to shed light on the phenomenon being studied. The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the experiences of the seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?
2. What are the ways of coping of seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?
3. What are the insights of seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a qualitative research method was used to better understand the viewpoints of the participants. The target audience for this methodology was the qualitative researchers. It made use of thorough and targeted research of small groups of individuals to aid and assist the creation of hypotheses. Data gathered using interviews, observation, discussion, and representation. The acquired data was correctly evaluated and analyzed. Naturalistic, interpretative, and inductive approaches dominate qualitative research (Mayan, 2016). The techniques also enable the researcher to establish a rapport with the participants. The researcher may easily get in touch with the participants as a result, which improves the validity and dependability of the data.

The research design for this study was qualitative in nature. It is for the purpose of exploring and understanding the experiences of seasoned reading coordinators in teaching struggling readers. I was able to acquire the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of the main participants by employing this design, which would not be feasible if I utilized qualitative research methodologies.

In the meantime, I utilized phenomenology which highlighted and pinpointed specific phenomena from the viewpoints of the actors embedded inside the given situation. From the human point of view, this was usually interpreted as an act of collecting deep information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as discussions and participant observation, interviews, and representing this from the points of view of the research participants (Lune and Berg, 2017).

I employed phenomenology as it was greatly suitable in this academic endeavor. I realized the necessity to perform phenomenological research in the local context, given that my study solely attempted to account the lived experiences of the participants in this study, who were elementary teachers. Additionally, this study method allowed me to delve further into the lives of the informants and participants.

Participants

The key participants of this study were the seasoned reading coordinators in Municipality of Kapalong. The selection of participants is justified because the intended participants of the study were seasoned reading coordinators or teachers who had been in the teaching a struggling reader. Thus, they were the only ones capable of providing authentic accounts about the research topic. According to the criteria of the study, fourteen (14) participants were come from different elementary schools in Municipality of Kapalong. The researcher was conducted in-depth interviews with all fourteen (14) individuals, doing one-on-one or online interviews with each participant. This number was chosen in accordance with Cresswell's (2013) recommendation that there should be between (3) and (15) participants in a phenomenological study. By incorporating this group of participants in a qualitative research study, data saturation was attained in the data gathering procedure.

The participants in this study were chosen based on a specified pre-inclusion criterion. Regarding those requirements, the ideal participants had the following traits: (1) They must be a licensed professional teacher in a public elementary school in Municipality of Kapalong; (2) they must be a reading coordinator in English or Filipino subject; and (3) they support struggling reader for minimum of 5 years in teaching service.

Procedure

As a researcher, I went through a series of processes to gathered data and other essential information for the study. Before starting the study, I sought advice from my adviser to determine how and what steps would be necessary to complete it. In this way, even before

the study began, I had planned ahead of time.

I ensured that the data gathering processes were conducted accurately to facilitate a smooth analysis and interpretation process. I make sure to establish contact with the individuals I intended to interview and confirmed their availability. Initially, I sought permission to conducted research with a group of ten elementary teachers who were identified for this study. Since the participants were teachers from public schools, I personally inform them about the research. It is important for me to clearly communicate the purpose and goals of my study to the participants.

Before the actual interviews, the participants can be informed about the purpose of the study. In this qualitative research, interviews were the primary methods employed for data collection. As described by Smith et al. (2013), these qualitative data gathering approaches aimed to provided valuable insights into the underlying processes and changes in individuals' perspectives. As the researcher, it was important for me to have a clear understanding of the research nature and purpose to introduce the participants and seek their consent to participate in the study.

Ensuring the trustworthiness of results was crucial aspect of conducting high- quality qualitative research. One technique recommended for assessing the credibility of findings is member checking, also referred to as participant or respondent validation. Member checking involves the process of sharing collected data or research findings with participants to verify their accuracy and alignment with their own experiences. This technique is often listed as one of several validation approaches in qualitative research (Birt et al., 2016).

In collecting data, I measured to ensure that the study's findings were ethically sound and trustworthy. My manuscript was sent to the research technical panel for a thorough evaluation. I wrote a permission letter addressed to the institution where I conducted my study after securing the approval of all panel members. Then I used the document to request authorization from the appropriate institution, specifically the Office of the President, to conduct the study.

Data Analysis

The gathered data in my research was presented and examined in my study depending on the research's objectives or goals. This necessitates a thorough examination of the content of the participant's responses to arrive at the study's conclusions. As a result, the goal of data analysis was to look for common patterns that could provide ideas that could answer the research questions posed in this study.

Moreover, the data collected in the study was systematically organized and stored by the researcher using technical resources. The audio and video recorders were utilized to capture the conversation. Working, organizing, and combining material into manageable pieces; synthesizing, searching for patterns, and discussing what was significant and what is to learned are all part of qualitative analysis. The researcher conducted a qualitative content analysis to provide a more thorough analysis of the study. Content analysis involves the study of making inferences from a text to other states or qualities of the source using a repeatable and precise procedure. Following the research analysis, all examined information was derived from a genuine source, which was the informants.

Thematic analysis was used in this study to analyze the collected and acquired data. During the data-gathering phase, the goal was to find any patterns that represent concepts that the participants represent. The information was sorted into logical categories that summarize and make sense of the note's manuscript. Thematic analysis was a flexible qualitative analytical method that allowed the researcher to derive new ideas and concepts from data.

Moreover, thematic analysis was a good research approach when trying to find out something about people's views, opinions, knowledge, experiences, or values from a set of qualitative data such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey responses. Thematic analysis was adaptable, and what researchers do with the themes once they have been discovered varies depending on the research goals and the analysis process. Many academics utilized theme analysis to come closer to their data and had a better understanding of the content.

Furthermore, I completed the procedures of familiarizing the data, producing initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining, and identifying themes, and constructing the report. The analytical procedure began with transcription. Separate it into bits or elements by analyzing it. It is a process in which the researcher attempts to make sense of the data he or she has gathered.

Finally, I listened to the recorded interviews of my participants and transcribed them to facilitate the coding process later on. I reviewed the data multiple times to familiarize myself with the responses and quickly identify the most common ones. I aggregated these common responses and derived a few themes, which I further refined to a select few. I employed data reduction techniques to eliminate irrelevant data and repurpose it as valuable study material for readers to understand. I sort and organize a substantial amount of qualitative data, enabling me to integrate and categorize it efficiently. Data display techniques are utilized to present the data in matrices, charts, and graphs, allowing readers to draw their conclusions.

Ethical Considerations

When gathering data from individuals, scientists and researchers must always abide by a set of ethical principles that serve as a guide for research designs and procedures. Understanding real-world occurrences, researching potent therapies, examining behavior, and enhancing lives in other ways are frequently the objectives of human research. Ethical guidelines must be observed when doing

research. These factors function to uphold academic or scientific integrity, increase the validity of the research, and protect the rights of research participants (Bhandari, 2022).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that emphasizes consideration for other people and acknowledges their inherent autonomy. By giving participants enough information about the nature and purpose of this research study in the participant's information leaflet in a comprehensible way to improve their informed consent, the concept of autonomy can be upheld (Kalu & Bwalya, 2017).

In this study, an informed consent form was created in advance for the participants. The form provided detailed information about the study, allowing interested individuals to learn more about it. During the interviews, the researcher respected the opinions and perspectives of the participants. It was crucial to establish a respectful relationship with the participants, considering their viewpoints, culture, and way of life, and giving them the choice to participate or not. The participants were always respected, as their importance was prioritized over the study. Before each interview, the researcher sought permission to record the entire conversation and the participants' responses. Additionally, the participants were informed of their rights to be informed about the study results.

Consent was formalized in order to protect people's right to choose whether or not to engage in the research, and to foster research interactions that were built on "trust and integrity." A person's decision to participate in the research needed to be voluntary and based on accurate knowledge about the implications of their involvement (Klykken, 2021). Ensuring the validity of consent was a fundamental requirement in the past.

In this study, the participants were encouraged to make informed choices and voluntarily participate, adhering to ethical research standards. They were informed of their rights, including the right to ask questions during the interview, the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and the right to leave the interview without providing an explanation. If a participant chose to leave in the middle of the interview, the researcher respected their decision. The researcher ensured that every participant was enthusiastic and motivated to contribute to the success of the study. During the interviews, the researcher obtained consent to record the entire conversation to capture a comprehensive understanding of their experiences.

Beneficence emphasizes that the study should be beneficial to those who would participate in it rather than risky. This research prioritizes the safety and well-being of participants above any potential financial gain. To ensure participant anonymity and minimize risk, all identifying information will be removed from the data. Throughout the research process, participant safety was paramount, and all data files were securely stored and never left unattended or unsecured (Kirsh, 2019).

The researcher secured a safe location for conducting face-to-face interviews, prioritizing the safety of all participants. During the interviews, participants were provided a secure environment where they could freely share their stories without fear of rejection or criticism. To mitigate psychological risks, the information gathered during the interviews was kept confidential and secure, minimizing the potential for negative outcomes such as shame or embarrassment. The researcher followed safety protocols to prevent the transmission of COVID-19 between the interviewer and participants during the interviews.

Confidentiality is concerned in the research and findings, as well as participant safety. The participants' identities were concealed. To ensure participant confidentiality, all research materials, including video recordings, transcribed interviews, and notes, will be securely destroyed after data analysis is complete. Some participants initially expressed hesitation about being interviewed due to uncertainty about what to share. However, after assuring them of the confidentiality of their statements, they felt comfortable and open in responding to interview questions. This research was conducted with the utmost respect and sensitivity, and I took great care in formulating questions to ensure a comfortable and respectful experience for all participants.

I made sure that each participant was identified using discrete coding. This provision was based on Republic Act 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which specifies that any information that could be used to identify participants by name, gender, ethnicity, or occupation should be appropriately written to protect participant anonymity. As a result, suitable coding and other safeguards were implemented to secure the participants' identities. In addition, none of my research participants were ever obliged to provide their names on any of the study's forms. The researcher also conducted a firsthand transcription of the interviews. Research data shall be stored and be destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Justice relates to the idea that everyone who were involved in this study should be treated fairly. In my situation, I made sure that the participants were picked fairly using the correct method of participant selection, which was a purposive sampling method. It necessitates a fair distribution of risks and benefits as part of the research findings.

To ensure justice, the participants were not required to spend any money as their contribution to the research was acknowledged. The researcher recognized the importance of all participants and credited them for their valuable contributions to the study. Their efforts were fully appreciated, and as a gesture of gratitude, practical tokens were provided to express appreciation for their involvement in the research.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts. Part one focused on the participant's data, from which qualitative data were collected. Part two covered the data analysis procedures and the steps involved in categorizing the emergent themes from the results of the in-depth

interviews. Part three focused on the responses to the interview questions about each research problem. Lastly, part four provided a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of this study were the seasoned reading coordinators in fourteen public schools in the Municipality of Kapalong Davao del Norte. As shown in Table 1, a total of fourteen (14) individuals took part in this study, comprising 14 female participants for in-depth interviews. Among these 14 participants, each reading coordinators were assigned to teach from a different school.

In-depth Interview. There were fourteen (14) key participants in this study. All of these participants were reading coordinators located in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. To uphold the principles of confidentiality, each participant was assigned a pseudonym during the in-depth interview, following the approach employed by Bernal (2014). These pseudonyms were chosen by the participants themselves based on their preferences and the unique characteristics that emerged during the interview sessions.

The selected pseudonyms provided insight into the characteristics and qualities of the participants. For instance, Tutor earned her nickname due to her role in instructing and guiding students. Pulse received her nickname reflecting her lively and engaging teaching style. Mentor was named for her mentorship aspect of teaching and the impact of shaping young minds. Expert earned her nickname due to her expertise in teaching struggling readers. Champion was named for her students' success and growth in the classroom setting. Leader received her nickname which signifies her leadership in fostering the learning development of struggling readers. Guide received her nickname illustrating the role of guiding and imparting knowledge to her students who are in need.

Furthermore, Sage earned her nickname due to her perceptive responses implying wisdom and knowledge in guiding students through their studies. Ally was named for her being supportive of her students' academic journey. Wisdom received her nickname due to her ability to impart knowledge respectfully. Pro was chosen for the participants who skillfully in the field of education especially handling a struggling reader. Caring earned her nickname due to her genuine concern for the students. Wise received her nickname due to her wise strategy in handling struggling readers and giving the students a life lesson. Echo was named for her lasting knowledge in teaching the students.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Tutor	36	5	Female	IDI-01
Pulse	39	7	Female	IDI-02
Mentor	46	10	Female	IDI-03
Expert	35	6	Female	IDI-04
Champion	43	13	Female	IDI-05
Leader	42	5	Female	IDI-06
Guide	37	8	Female	IDI-07
Sage	45	6	Female	IDI-08
Ally	46	9	Female	IDI-09
Wisdom	41	7	Female	IDI-10
Pro	48	8	Female	IDI-11
Caring	45	7	Female	IDI-12
Wise	38	5	Female	IDI-13
Echo	48	8	Female	IDI-14
Total=14				

All participants answered the same set of questions. The selection of participants was based on their involvement and experiences as seasoned reading coordinators, which were identified by the researcher and verified through personal declarations provided by the participants.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face for it to be more personal and engaging, allowing for deeper insights and better interpretation of non-verbal cues. Additionally, immediate clarification and follow-up questions can be addressed, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the participant's experiences. Most of the participants did ask for a hardcopy which was distributed to their respective schools as per request. The researcher respected the participant's decision when asked to adjust and reschedule the interview due to their important reasons related to their profession. The researcher did consider face-to-face as an important factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews, the interview responses were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis commenced with the coding process, which involved organizing the materials into segments of texts to derive meaningful information. Through coding, descriptions of the participants' settings and thematic categories were generated to shape an overall depiction of the phenomenon under study. Data results were presented in the form of a table. This data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

In the data analysis, I followed the second step by categorizing the data and presenting it in Table 2. The themes were organized according to the research questions and referred to as central themes, while the opposing significant themes were represented as co-ideas from the participants' responses. Additionally, the table included a column indicating the frequency of the responses, which served as the basis for classifying them into general, typical, and variant categories, as discussed above. Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of the seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?

To answer this research question, in-depth interview was conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences regarding handling struggling readers.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 are presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: difficulty in developing fundamental literacy skills, reading comprehension difficulties, lack of parental support, and struggle in aligning strategies with student's reading ability.

Table 2. *Lived Experiences of Seasoned Reading Coordinators in Handling Struggling Readers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Difficulty in Developing Fundamental Literacy Skills	<p>"My common experience was that I felt pity. It is a pity, especially since they have reached a higher grade, but they still struggle with their reading. The worst part of this is that they do not even know the basic sounds."-IDI-01</p> <p>"There are many struggling readers here, and what I noticed about them is that they cannot really identify sounds. Maybe their mother directly introduces BA but not the sounds, because as the reading coordinator, I noticed that it is easier for the child if they know how to identify the sounds."-IDI-02</p> <p>"We have encountered many struggles in working with struggling readers, so for example, if there is no retention of what they read, then low decoding ability."-IDI-03</p> <p>"There is a student who knows how to read but cannot comprehend and has no speed when reading, and even though they have reached the higher grade, it is still difficult for them to identify the letter sounds and letter names."-IDI-06</p> <p>"When working with struggling readers, what I often experience is that they have difficulty decoding. Those who do not know how to read get confused when I ask them about letter sounds."-IDI-10</p> <p>"So struggling readers are those readers that are frustrated. At first, I was a grade 3 teacher, and my experience is that there are students who don't even know the letter names and letter sounds. As a grade 3 teacher, it is difficult for me because they don't even know how to read, and most of them have a problem; either they have a manifestation resulting in them not memorizing the alphabet, letter names, and letter sounds."-IDI-14</p>
Reading Comprehension Difficulties	<p>"A child will be behind because they struggle with reading as well as their comprehension. They cannot participate because of the hindrance of not being able to read and understand."-IDI-01</p> <p>"Struggling readers are those struggling readers, or it can be because of frustration; they can read but they cannot comprehend, so inside the class, they cannot participate because they cannot read, and this kind of learner often has very low comprehension, resulting in very poor grades and also a lack grade-level content, and there is a reason why students are difficult to read and one of the reasons is that the parent itself, if their parents have less support, especially in their learning because they are busy"-IDI-11</p>
Struggle in Aligning Strategies with Student's Reading Ability	<p>"Actually, in handling struggling readers, it is difficult for us, especially when we talk about a strategy, because there are many strategies that can be applied to them, but we cannot decide what strategy we are going to implement for the struggling readers."-IDI-04</p> <p>"Of course, when I deal with a struggling reader, there is a possibility of how I am going to attack the students who cannot read or what strategy I am going to use with them."- IDI-05</p> <p>"Okay, in my own experience in handling struggling readers, it is difficult for my part as a teacher to implement a strategy for their needs because there are students who already know how to read, so it is difficult to find a way or strategy on how we could handle them."-IDI-08</p> <p>"One of my experiences working with struggling readers is that I get confused about what strategy I am going to use to address their difficulty in reading and how I am going to adopt this strategy because I have used a lot of strategies but still cannot learn."-IDI-09</p> <p>"When it comes to experiences, of course, you are going to handle the struggling readers. It is quite difficult because they are still struggling and it is difficult to find a strategy that suits them, and you must assist to their level, and you also have to deeply understand what would be the reason behind this."-IDI-13</p>

Difficulty in Developing Fundamental Literacy Skills

The theme encompasses the challenges that reading coordinators face in handling struggling readers, particularly in reading and understanding the basic phonetics of the language. The participants of the study shared their experiences highlighting the range of

challenges they have encountered. Thus, they mention their challenges including dealing with students who are still having difficulty in identifying the letter names and letter sounds, and those students that are already reached a higher grade but still do not even know how to read. Their personal experiences have enabled them to recognize and understand the challenges involved in teaching reading to struggling readers.

Based on the experiences of Tutor (pseudonym), she expresses deep concern about the struggle many students face in acquiring basic literacy skills, even, when they progress to higher grades.

“My common experiences was malooy ko, naa jud ang kalooy especially naabot na sila’g higher grade na naa jud nag struggle gihapon sa ilahang reading, worst is kana bitaw’ng dili najud sila kabalo sa mga sounds, pero kana jud pinaka worst jud nga experience kay kanang niabot na siya og higher grade nga dili pa siya kabalo mag identify og letter sounds”. (IDI-01)

(My common experience was that I felt pity. It is a pity, especially since they have reached a higher grade, but they still struggle with their reading. The worst part of this is that they do not even know the basic sounds)

As with the other participants Pulse (pseudonym), narrated her experiences about the key issue for many struggling readers is a lack of understanding of the basic sounds that make up words, which is a crucial aspect of learning to read. This challenge if their parents continue to introduce letters without focusing on the sounds, it may make it harder for children to learn to read.

“Naay daghan struggling readers pero ang akong nakuanan sa ila mag struggle jud sila pag kana ganing dili jud sila maka identify sa sounds, siguro pud sa way kana ganing moditso siguro ang mama og introduce kana mao na siya BA, pero wala nila gikuan ang unsay sounds niya kay napansin nako sa akoang pag ka reading coor. Masdali ang bata pag maka identify jud siya sa sounds”. (IDI-02)

(There are many struggling readers here, and what I noticed about them is that they cannot really identify sounds. Maybe their mother directly introduces BA but not the sounds, because as the reading coordinator, I noticed that it is easier for the child if they know how to identify the sounds).

In addition, Mentor (pseudonym), highlighted her experiences encountered while working with struggling readers, particularly in terms of reading comprehension and decoding ability. From her experiences it suggests that these difficulties can hinder their ability to understand and retain information from texts, making it harder for them to engage with and benefit from reading materials.

“We have encountered many experiences in working struggling readers so for example of that is no retention of what they read, then low decoding ability po”. (IDI-03)

(We have encountered many struggles in working with struggling readers, for example, if there is no retention of what they read, then low decoding ability).

Moreover, Leader (pseudonym), stated her experiences particularly faced by a student who can read but struggles with reading comprehension, reading speed, and letter identification.

“Kanang naay bata nga kabalo magbasa pero dili kasabot walay comprehension unya mobasa lage siya pero walay speed hinay kaayo, bisag taas na iyahang age pero sa mga sounds or letter name mag lisud pa siya daghan jud na diri “. IDI-06

(There is a student who knows how to read but cannot comprehend and has no speed when reading, and even though they have reached a higher grade, it is still difficult for them to identify the letter sounds and letter names).

Furthermore, Wisdom (pseudonym), stated that decoding is what she often observed when working with struggling readers and students often get confused when she asked about the letter sounds.

“When working struggling readers mga kasagaran experience nako is difficulty with decoding, kanang mga dili kabalo mobasa maglisud siya og pangutan on nimo siya sa mga letter sounds, maglibog siya”. (IDI-10)

(When working with struggling readers, what I often experience is that they have difficulty decoding. Those who don’t know how to read get confused when I ask them about letter sounds).

Lastly, Echo (pseudonym), highlights her experience that struggling readers are those who experience frustration and difficulty in reading. The participant, who is a grade 3 teacher shares her experience of encountering students who lack basic knowledge of letter names and sounds. This lack of fundamental skills makes it challenging for her to teach reading effectively.

“So struggling readers are those readers that are frustration so ang experience nako ani sa ilaha at first naa man ko sa grade 3, naa jud bata nga miskan letter dili jud kaila sa letter name usahay letter sound dili sila kaila, so as grade 3 teacher hard kaayo sa among part nga grade 3 na dili pa sila kabasa kasagaran pud ana nga mga bata naa jud na silay problema, naa silay manifestation nga dili nila ma memorize ang alphabet letter name or alphabet letter sound”. (IDI-14)

(So struggling readers are those readers who are frustrated. At first, I was a grade 3 teacher, and my experience is that there are students who do not even know the letter names and letter sounds. As a grade 3 teacher, it is difficult for me because they do not even know how to read, and most of them have a problem; either they have a manifestation resulting in them not memorizing the alphabet, letter

names, and letter sounds.)

Reading Comprehension Difficulties

This theme talks about reading comprehension difficulties and its impact on a child's overall academic performance. The participants express the difficulties they encounter in working with struggling readers. They mention that some children face challenges in both reading and comprehension of texts, as a result, they struggle to actively participate in learning activities. The inability to read and understand hinders their ability to fully engage with the material being taught.

Based on the experience of Tutor (pseudonym), she expresses that one of the challenges she faced is when the children struggle with reading and comprehension they fall behind in their overall educational journey. Their inability to read and understand becomes a hindrance that prevents them from actively participating in classroom activities.

“So, kani siya is ma behind jud ang bata kay struggled man ilahang reading itself pag ila sa letter sa words, dili pud sila kabasa samot na ilang comprehension. So ma behind jud sila dili sila kasagaran maka participate because of the hindrance nga dili sila kabasa kay dili man sila kasabot.” (IDI-01)

(A child will be behind because they struggle with reading as well as their comprehension. They cannot participate because of the hindrance of not being able to read and understand)

As with the other participants, Mentor (pseudonym) narrated her experience when working with struggling readers, she stated that struggling readers are individuals who may be able to read words, but they struggle to understand the meaning behind the text. These learners often have low comprehension skills, leading to poor grades and limited participation in classroom discussion.

“Struggling readers learners mao na siya ang struggling in reading learning no or under sa frustration, kabasa pero naa jud problema hinay unya dili jud kaabalo mo understand so inside the classroom first dili ni siya maka participate of course dili gani siya makabasa diba, so this kind of learner is kasagaran jud ani very low comprehension resulting to a very poor grades and also lack of participation in the classroom discussion”.(IDI-03)

(Struggling readers are those struggling readers, or it can be because of frustration; they can read but they cannot comprehend, so inside the class they cannot participate because they cannot read, and this kind of learner often has very low comprehension, resulting in very poor grades and also a lack of participation in the classroom discussion.)

In addition to Expert (pseudonym) experience, she expressed that individuals with weak comprehension skills have a different level of participation compared to proficient readers, students are struggle to understand the discussion and instructions, which hinders their ability to effectively communicate and engage with others in the classroom.

“Kanang lahi rajud no sa lahi raman jud ilahang participation during sa i compare nato sa mga reader najud kay kanang labi nag og english ang classroom intruction kay hina jud sila sa ilang comprehension , syempre unsaon nimo pag communicate kung dili sila kasabot ug dili sila kabasa sa imong ginatudlo”. (IDI-04)

(Their participation is really different compared to those readers, especially if the classroom instruction is in English. Their comprehension is weak, so how can you communicate with them if they cannot understand your discussion).

Moreover, Champion (pseudonym) stated her experience in working with struggling readers, according to her some students can read but struggle with comprehension, and this is categorized as a comprehension issue. On the other hand, if students cannot read and also struggle with comprehension, they are classified as being under frustration.

“Naa poy uban bata nga makabasa sila pero dili sila kasabot mao nay comprehension, now ang phil iri man gud is kung dili ka kabasa unya dili pajud ka comprehend didto najud ka sa frustration”. (IDI-05)

(Some other students know how to read but cannot comprehend, so that is comprehension. Now, in Phil-IRI, it means that if you do not know how to read as well as cannot comprehend, you are automatically frustrated).

Lastly, Wisdom (pseudonym) expressed that when there are struggling readers in the class, they tend to fall behind compared to the smarter students.

The smarter students are able to easily grasp and understand the lessons being taught, while the struggling readers find it difficult to comprehend and follow along.

“In my experience kung unsa may epekto sa mga struggling readers kung panahon jud sa klase mabitin jud sila kay kung moingon ka nag klase ko karon naa man jud mga bright na bata, ang mga bright baya dali lang maka catch up samantalang akong mga struggling reader maglisud jud sila wala man sila kahibalo unsa akong gipanglitok mabitin jud sila pag ayo”. (IDI-10)

(In my experience, the effect of struggling readers when I have my class is that they will be behind because in class there are smart students, and smart students can easily catch up on the lesson while my struggling readers find it difficult to understand what I am talking about).

Lack of Parental Support

The theme explores the challenges faced by reading coordinators in the parental support of a child's reading. The participants of the study shared the experiences they encountered in the area of reading. They mention the challenges of the children who lack parental support due to various circumstances including separation, working abroad, parents being non-readers, or being raised by grandparents. These challenges often lead to struggles in reading coordinators to accommodate these students, particularly in their reading.

Based on the experiences of Tutor (pseudonym), she expressed that one of the challenges that she faced was the lack of parental support for her students. She mentioned that regardless of her students' personal circumstances she ensures that all of her students become proficient readers.

"As reading teacher it is your responsibility to make all your learner become a reader mangita jud kag mga ways kung unsaon nimo siya pagpaagi, so nag background check ko so mostly katong jud mga dili kabasa kaayo mas nag struggle jud sa reading. kuan jud naa silay mga problem sa ilahang balay, most of them kay hiwalay ang parents, ang uban kay nag abroad, nag puyo lang sa mga lolo lola ana".(IDI-01)

(As a reading teacher, it is your responsibility to make all your learners become readers. You need to find ways to teach them, so I do background checks, and most of the struggling readers have a problem at home; most of their parents are separated, abroad, or solely raised by their grandparents).

As with the other participants, Mentor (pseudonym) expressed her experience when working with struggling readers, she stated her role as an educator in addressing literacy issues not just within the confines of the school, but extending to the students' homes as well. In addition, according to her, it is a challenge for her to teach a student whose parents are also illiterate.

"So we are ready to give a priority to addressed to their reading needs by doing home visitation so gina monitor jud na namo sila unya. To monitor their reading skills and also we extend our services sometimes man gud maabot sa balay makita namo nga kanang pati parents dili gyud kabasa so problem jud sya unsaon pagtudlo sa anak nga dili gane sila kabasa, so naa man gud mi naka arrange nga lesson". (IDI-03)

(So, we are ready to give priority to addressing their reading needs by doing home visits, so we always monitor them. To monitor their reading skills, sometimes we extend our services because in their home we can see that their parents also are unable to read, so that was a problem on how they could teach their child, so we have lessons that are already arranged).

In addition, Mentor (pseudonym) narrated that one of the challenges she encountered was the lack of parental support for students, especially those who are struggling with reading. She mentions that some students are from broken families or have parents who work abroad, making it difficult for them to provide the necessary assistance for their children's learning.

"My common experiences kay mostly after sa pandemic almost 3 years na siguro sya, grabi jud ang kanang challenge sa amoa as reading coordinators kay syempre home based man ilahang klase ang reading sa ilahang balay wala kaayo na sa mga ginikanan na focus no kay syempre ang mga ginikanan mag trabaho nya busy. labi na broken family nya mostly diria kay ang mga parents og mama kay abroad". (IDI-04)

(My common experience as a reading coordinator was that when the pandemic came, it was almost three (3) years that students were home-based learning and reading in their homes. They could not focus because their parents were busy at work and some come from broken families and most parents are abroad).

Furthermore, Leader (pseudonym) expressed the experience she noticed regarding parental involvement. She stated that in school students can be provided with education but at the student's home, there are no parents to follow up, resulting to a child's struggles in reading.

"Kanang daghan man jud mga struggling readers diri kay tungod sa pandemic ba, unya struggling siya in terms anang sa balay walay follow up, motudlo ta diri sa school unya pag abot sa balay walay follow up gikan sa parents maong maglisud jud ang bata in terms sa reading wala jud follow up sa parents". (IDI-06)

(There are many struggling readers here because of the pandemic, and there is no follow-up from the parents. At school, they can be taught, but when they come home, there is no parent to follow up with, so the child might really struggle in terms of reading).

Lastly, Pro (pseudonym) explained that one of the reasons for students finding it difficult to read is the lack of parental support, particularly when parents are busy and unable to provide adequate assistance with their child's learning.

"Okay for elementary maam it reduced academic achievement so struggling readers may experience challenges in understanding grade level content and naa jud mga rason nganong ang bata maglisud sa ilang pagbasa isa na ana ka rason kung ang mga ginikanan kulang og suporta labi na sa ilang pagtuon tapos dili matutukan ang pagbasa tungod sa ka busy sa mga ginikanan". IDI-11

(Okay, for elementary, it reduced academic achievement, so struggling readers may experience challenges in understanding grade-level content, and there is a reason why students are difficult to read, and one of the reasons is that the parent itself, if their parents have less

support, especially in their learning because they are busy).

Struggle in Aligning Strategies with Student's Reading Ability

The theme encompasses the challenges and uncertainties faced by the reading coordinator particularly when it comes to selecting and implementing appropriate strategies for struggling readers. The participants of the study highlight their experiences in tailoring strategies to meet the unique needs of struggling readers and feel uncertain about which strategy will be the most effective and beneficial for a particular student. This theme involves the challenges, of finding suitable strategies, assisting students at their level, and providing individualized support.

Based on Echo's (pseudonym) experience, she expressed that handling struggling readers is really difficult because there is a wide range of options in selecting strategy but it makes it challenging to determine the most appropriate strategy for each student.

"Actually sa pag handle og struggling readers lisud jud siya para sa amoa labi na og strategy najud ang istoryahan because daghan og strategy nga pwede ma apply sa ilaha but we can't decide of what strategy we are going to handle to the struggling readers". (IDI-14)

(Actually, in handling struggling readers, it is difficult for us, especially when we talk about a strategy, because there are many strategies that can be applied to them, but we cannot decide what strategy we are going to implement for the struggling readers).

As with the other participants, Champion (pseudonym) stated her experience regarding finding the appropriate strategy for her students who are struggling in reading.

"Ahh syempre kanang pag mag kuan kog mga struggling naa jud ang kanang unsaon pag tira anang mga bata nga dili kabasa or unsa nga strategy ang angay sa ilaha". (IDI-05)

(Of course, when I deal with a struggling reader, there is a possibility of how I am going to attack the students who can't read or what strategy I am going to use with them.)

In addition, according to Sage's (pseudonym) experience, she finds it challenging to implement strategies for struggling readers because there are some students who already know how to read.

"Okay in my own experience in handling struggling readers lisud sa akong part as a teacher nga mag implement og strategy nga para sa ilahang needs kay naa man gud mga bata nga kabalo na mag basa so lisud siya pangitaan og pamaagi kung unsaon namo sila paghandle". (IDI-08)

(Okay, in my own experience in handling struggling readers, it is difficult for my part as a teacher to implement a strategy for their needs because there are students who already know how to read, so it is difficult to find a way or strategy on how we could handle them).

Furthermore, Ally (pseudonym) narrated her difficulties when it comes to selecting a strategy for her students who are struggling in reading. She mentioned that she feeling confused and frustrated when working with struggling readers who are not making process despite trying various strategies.

"kanang struggling readers isa sa akong na experience is maglibog ko kung unsa ang mga strategy na pwede nako buhaton para ma address nako ilang kalisud sa pagbasa og kanang unsaon nako pag adopt ani nga strategy because I use a lot of strategy pero ngano dili gihapon sila makabalo". (IDI-09)

(One of my experiences working with struggling readers is that I get confused about what strategy I am going to use to address their difficulty in reading and how I am going to adopt this strategy because I have used a lot of strategies but still cannot learn).

Lastly, Wise (pseudonym) shared her experience regarding the difficulty she faced when working with struggling readers. According to her, it is challenging to find a strategy that is well-suited to the individual needs of struggling readers considering their strengths and learning style to determine the most appropriate interventions for them.

"When it comes to experiences syempre you are going to handle the struggling readers medyo lisud jud siya kay syempre nag struggle paman jud na sila, then lisud is mangita kag strategies kung unsay pwede sa ilaha, mag assist ka sa ilaha kung unsa ang ilahang level unya you also have to deeply understand kung unsa ang reason ana". (IDI-13)

(When it comes to experiences, of course, you are going to handle the struggling readers. It was quite difficult because they are still struggling and it was difficult to find a strategy that suits them, and you must assist to their level, and you also have to deeply understand what would be the reason behind this).

Research Question No. 2: What are the ways of coping of seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?

This question focused on understanding the coping mechanisms employed by reading coordinators to address the challenges they encounter in handling struggling readers. It was revealed that they employ a range of strategies and techniques to overcome the difficulties.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 are presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: cultivating a supportive environment for struggling readers, be consistent in teaching the struggling readers, maintaining positive reinforcement and motivation in teaching and fostering collaboration and community engagement in reading programs. Cultivating a Supportive Environment for Struggling Readers

This theme focuses of the fundamental importance of creating a positive, encouraging, and supportive learning environment to effectively assist struggling readers. It emphasizes that creating a positive learning environment and fostering a love for reading, the learning process for struggling readers can become less difficult. The participants of the study highlights that when students enjoy reading and feel supported, they are likely to be more receptive to learning and implementing reading strategies.

Based on the statement of Expert (pseudonym) she highlights the need to be lively and friendly when interacting with her students who are struggling with reading. She mentioned that to make students feel comfortable, reduce any feelings of intimidation so that their learning process becomes less difficult.

Table 3. *How the Seasoned Reading Coordinators Coped with the Challenges they have Encounter in Handling Struggling Readers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Cultivating a Supportive Environment for Struggling Readers	<p>“So that the struggling readers will not be intimidated by you, you must be lively and friendly, and your emotions should be stable, like smiling always and not being strict, so that their learning will also not be difficult.”- IDI-04</p> <p>“You need to put in your mind that this work is not just work but make the student feel that you love them like they cannot be afraid if you call them to read. The teacher is already emotionally prepared to meet the needs of the students, so just accept who they are and not just look for work but the fashion itself.”- IDI-07</p> <p>To make sure they feel supported and encouraged in the learning journey, we must build trusting relationships, ensure they are patient and understanding, acknowledge or appreciate their progress regularly, and celebrate even a small achievement to boost their confidence and motivation.”-IDI-08</p> <p>“I have suggested to the new teacher that you must have a personal connection with your pupils and continue learning; do not let work overshadow your personal life; and most of all, you must be more patient and love your work.”-IDI-10</p>
Be Consistent in teaching the Struggling readers	<p>“Just be consistent and teach them first the letter sounds, because once a child learns the sounds, they can blend until they can follow other things in reading.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“Just accept the challenge, never give up, and have consistent communication and follow up with your struggling readers for you to reach out and give them what kind of reading they do not have.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“Always do a repetition, not just because you like it, but make it your strategy to teach them how to read and repeat it every day, especially letter names and letter sounds.”- IDI-06</p> <p>“It is always repetition that makes a child learn; the content may be repeated, but the approach varies.”-IDI-09</p> <p>“Just be permanent, ma’am. Although your style may not be permanent, be consistent in monitoring the reading ability of your learners, and your activities must be consistent. Consistency is the first tip that you need to have, and never stop teaching them even though they already know it.”-IDI-14</p>
Maintaining Positive Reinforcement and Motivation in Teaching	<p>“Just have heart-to-heart communication, like positivity, that you can read. We will work hard for you to read, and I will encourage them by saying, if you can read, you can go anywhere and you do not lose. Just a simple way of living because reading can be applied to living.”-IDI-01</p> <p>“Just like what I have said earlier, I will not say a negative word that can be insulting to them but encourage them to continue because I told them that it is important to know how to read because if you can read, you can go anywhere and you do not lose.”- IDI-02</p> <p>“Just use a lot of motivation if you want, like stars, or if your struggling readers are higher grades, just give them a reward system. For me, a notebook and ballpoint pen will make them happy, and food is also one.”-IDI-05</p> <p>“Just tell them that they already know, but you still need to practice more in your home to perfect your reading. Just don’t say a negative word because it can lower their self- esteem.”-IDI-06</p> <p>“Do not work just for the salary. Since I have a quote that I really hold: “As a child, the way of life is to learn, and as an adult, our way of life is to teach, then as a teacher, our way of life is to make our students better than what we are.”-IDI-14</p>
Fostering Collaboration and Community Engagement in Reading Programs	<p>“Be yourself; do not be shy to ask for help from your fellow because if you are new, just do not be ashamed as long as you grow and ask how to teach a struggling child, like ma’am, how to do this because they know, especially when you are in the higher grade, ma’am, what the problem is with this child. So, they all know, just do not be shy to ask your co-teacher who knows what this child is.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“The reading coordinator needs to lead and guide the reading program within the school, including collaborating with teachers, the school head, and other stakeholders. Finally, a genuine passion for literacy and a dedication to helping students become proficient readers are essential qualities for reading coordinators to inspire and motivate others in the school community.”-IDI-08</p> <p>“As a reading coordinator, you must coordinate with your co-teachers, school head, and other stakeholders, like parents, because you cannot do all the tasks on your own. It takes a community to raise a child.”- IDI-09</p>

“Effective communication skills are essential for building rapport with our pupils. Collaborating with colleagues and partnering with parents ensures that everyone involved in their education is informed and engaged.”- IDI-11
“Of course, we all know that in digging into the reader levels of our pupils, we should have the parents as partners, and then the teacher and learners need to work together in order to address and have better learning, especially in their reading.”-IDI-12

“Para dili pud ma intimidate sa imuha ang mga struggling readers, syempre dapat lively og friendly jud ka then stable lang imuhang emotion kanang mag smile dili jud ka ingon dragon kaayo no kay para ilahang learnings pud dili maglisod”. (IDI-04)

(So that the struggling readers will not be intimidated by you, you must be lively and friendly, and your emotions should be stable, like smiling always and not being strict, so that their learning will also not be difficult.)

As with the other participants, Guide (pseudonym) emphasizes the emotional aspect of teaching and the importance of creating a supportive, accepting, and loving environment for her struggling readers. According to her teaching is not just as a job, but as a vocation that involves forming emotional connections with students. She also stresses the importance of accepting students as they are, recognizing their individual strengths and weaknesses because this can help students feel valued and respected.

“Kinahanglan imuha jud ibutang sa hunahuna og kasing kasing nga imong trabaho, dili lang ni trabaho nga naga sweldo ka kumbaga imong jud i accept bata ba nga kana ganing ma feel jud pud sa bata ba nga love siya, kana ganing dili ko mahadlok kung tawagon ko ni maam kay magpabasa siya sa akoo, emotionally prepare naman jud ang mga teacher tanan unsay panginahanglan sa mga bata kanang i accept jud nimo siya kung unsa jud sila. Dili lang trabaho fashion jud sa trabaho ang imong ipakita.” (IDI-07)

(You need to put in your mind that this work is not just working but making the student feel that you love them like they cannot be afraid if you call them to read.

Actually, the teacher is already emotionally prepared to meet the needs of the students, so just accept who they are and not just look for work but the fashion itself).

In addition, Sage (pseudonym) highlights the importance of building a trusting and supportive relationship with struggling readers to enhance their learning journey. She mentioned the importance of being patient and understanding with struggling readers and acknowledging their progress even in a small achievement because it can encourage students to persevere and continue making progress.

“To sure they feel supported and encourage in the learning journey we must build trusting relationship, ensuring them patient and understanding acknowledge or appreciate their efforts in progress regularly jud then celebrate even small success to boost their confidence and motivation”. (IDI-08)

(To make sure they feel supported and encouraged in the learning journey, we must build trusting relationships, ensure they are patient and understanding, acknowledge or appreciate their progress regularly, and celebrate even a small achievement to boost their confidence and motivation).

Moreover, Wisdom (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of establishing a personal connection with her students. This involved getting to know them individually, understanding their interests and needs, and building a rapport based on trust and mutual understanding.

“I’ve suggest the new teacher you must have personal connection with your pupil and continue learning dont let work over shadow your personal life and most of all you must be more patient, love and love your work”. (IDI-10)

(I have suggested to the new teacher that you must have a personal connection with your pupils and continue learning; do not let work overshadow your personal life; and most of all, you must be more patient and love your work).

Be Consistent in teaching the Struggling readers

This theme focuses on the importance of consistency in teaching struggling readers. The participants mentioned that they need to be consistent in teaching particularly those students who struggled in reading. They also emphasize the importance of maintaining a regular and reliable approach when working with students who are facing challenges in reading. According to them, consistency helps struggling readers develop the necessary skills and build their confidence in reading.

Pulse’s (pseudonym) statement highlights the importance of consistency in teaching struggling readers, particularly focusing on teaching the letter sounds as a foundational skill. She stated that once children have a solid understanding of letter sounds, it becomes easier for the students to blend sounds and improve their reading abilities.

“Kanang consistent jud ka once nga itudlo nimo sa ilaha then dapat kabalo siya sa sound once man gud kabalo ang bata sa sounds, then maka blending na hantod masunod na niya tong uban sa reading”. (IDI-02)

(Just be consistent and teach them first the letter sounds because once a child learns the sounds, they can blend until they can follow other things in reading).

Moreover, Expert (pseudonym) expressed the significance of consistent communication and follow-up with her struggling readers. She also highlighted the importance of understanding the areas where struggling readers require additional support for her to tailor the instruction to meet the specific reading needs of each for her struggling readers.

“Accept the challenge and never give up and consistent communication and follow up sa mga struggling readers kay para makuan nimo sila ma reach out nimo og mahatag nimo ilang mga needs sa unsa nga mga klasi nga reading ilahang kulang”. (IDI-04)

(Just accept the challenge, never give up, and have consistent communication and follow up with your struggling readers so you to reach out and give them what kind of reading they do not have).

In addition, Leader (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of repetition as a teaching strategy for helping students learn to read specifically targeting the repetition of letter names and sounds.

“Balik balik rajud repetition nga kanang dili lang kay ganahan ka dapat everyday jud na nimo ng strategy magpabasa, everyday na balik balikon nako ang kanang letter jud og letter sounds”. (IDI-06)

(Always do a repetition, not just because you like it, but make it your strategy to teach them how to read and repeat it every day, especially letter names and letter sounds).

Furthermore, Ally (pseudonym) stated that repetition is significant in a child’s learning process. According to her repetition is the key to helping children learn and retain information. She also emphasized that content may be repeated but the approach to teaching may vary.

“Kanang it is always repetition nga ang bata maka tuon, kay sa content naga balik balik pero ang approach lahi lahi”. (IDI-09)

(It is always repetition that makes a child learn; the content may be repeated, but the approach varies).

Lastly, Echo (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of being consistent and persistent in teaching reading. According to her, consistency is the first tip that a teacher should possess when it comes to teaching reading, and never stop teaching even if the learners already have some knowledge or skills in reading.

“Kuan maam dapat kanang permanente gani, although dili permanente ang imuhang style pero dapat consistent ang imong monitoring sa reading ability sa imuhang mga bata unya dapat consistent ang imuhang activities padayon nga padayon, consistently maoy pinakauna jud nga tips na ihatag dapat dili ka mag undang never stop maskin kabalo na sila”. (IDI-14)

(Just be permanent, Ma’am. Although your style may not be permanent, be consistent in monitoring the reading ability of your learners, and your activities must be consistent. Consistency is the first tip that you need to have, and never stop teaching them even though they already know it).

Maintaining Positive Reinforcement and Motivation in Teaching

The theme encompasses the importance of maintaining positive reinforcement and motivation in teaching through connection between the students and the teacher and promoting the value of reading in various aspect of life. The participants of the study highlighted their coping mechanisms in handling struggling readers. Thus, they mention heart-to-heart communication, encouraging learners by emphasizing the benefits of reading and giving an appreciation for their progress.

During the interview, Tutor (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of positive reinforcement, motivation, and effective communication in teaching. She mentions that it is important to have a heart-to-heart communication style with her learners and provide them an encouragement to value the reading in every aspect of their lives.

“Heart to heart communication jud, kana bitaw’ng positivity nga makabasa lage ka no maningkamot lang ta nga makabasa ka, unya akoa pud silang gina encourage gina ing an nako siya nga kung makabasa man gud ka kaning makaadto ka bisan asa, maka dili ka masaag mga ana lang nga mga simple way in living ba kay ma apply man jud ang reading sa living”. (IDI-01)

(Just have heart-to-heart communication, like positivity, that you can read. We will work hard for you to read, and I will encourage them by saying, if you can read, you can go anywhere and you do not lose. Just a simple way of living because reading can be applied to living).

As with other participants, Pulse (pseudonym) highlights the importance of refraining from using negative words or insults that may discourage the learners. She also emphasizes the value of reading for the children like saying a positive word that can inspire her struggling readers and help them realize the opportunities that reading can bring.

“Kato akong giingon ganina nga kanang dili sila ingnon pa hinoon nga mura gani’g insulto niya pero kanang encourage lang jud sila gihapon nga padayon lang kumbaga nga ako man gud kuan sa ilaha nga importante man jud makabalo ka mo basa kay bisag asa muadto makabasa ka dili jud ka masaag ba”. (IDI-02)

(Just like what I have said earlier, I will not say a negative word that can be insulting to them but encourage them to continue because

I told them that it is important to know how to read because if you can read, you can go anywhere and you do not lose).

In addition, Champion (pseudonym) states the importance of using motivation and rewards to encourage and support learners in their reading journey. She believes that offering rewards can make struggling readers feel happy and motivated to engage in reading activities.

“Gamiti og daghan motivation kung gusto ka, stars o kung dagko naba na imong mga struggling reader no tagae pud og kanang reward system notebook man gud ako then ballpen kana malipay naman sila ana, food isa pud na food”. (IDI-05)

(Just use a lot of motivation if you want, like stars, or if your struggling readers have higher grades, just give them a reward system. For me, a notebook and ballpoint pen will make them happy, and food is also one.)

Moreover, Leader (pseudonym) highlights the idea that learners should be encouraged to respect their own reading abilities and recognize the value of practice. She also emphasized the need to avoid using negative words that can lower the self-esteem of struggling readers.

“Ingon lang jud nimo gang nga kanang “kabalo naman ka pero kailangan pa nimo mag practice sa inyuhang balay kay para ma perfect najud nimo imong pagbasa. Dili jud nimo ingon og dili maayo kay ma low man ang self esteem nila”. (IDI-06)

(Just tell them that they already know, but you still need to practice more in your home to perfect your reading. Just do not say a negative word because it can lower their self-esteem).

Lastly, Echo (pseudonym) highlights the importance of teaching as a vocation rather than just a job for a salary. She believes that the ultimate goal of teaching is to equip students with the skills, knowledge, and values that will enable them to commit student success and improvement.

“Do not work for money or for salary only kumbaga naa jud koy ginapanghawakan nga quotation nga kuan “as a child the way of life is to learn and as an adult our way of life is to teach then as a teacher our way of life is to make our students better than what we are.” (IDI-14)

(Do not work just for the salary. Since I have a quote that I really hold: “ As a child, the way of life is to learn, and as an adult, our way of life is to teach, then as a teacher, our way of life is to make our students better than what we are).

Fostering Collaboration and Community Engagement in Reading Programs

The theme encompasses the importance of collaboration and community engagement in enhancing reading programs in schools. The participants mentioned that in working with struggling readers it is essential to work closely with teachers, school heads, and stakeholders which include parents, and community leaders. They also emphasized that collaboration is crucial to ensure the success of the reading program, as it allows for the exchange of ideas, resources, and strategies that can improve the literacy levels among struggling readers.

During the interview, Mentor (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of communication, openness, and continuous learning in the context of teaching. She highlights the importance of seeking advice when dealing with struggling readers to address student challenges and improve teaching effectiveness.

“Be yourself dont be shy to ask for help from your fellow to kung bag-o pa gyud ta kanang ayaw jud kaulaw basta kay kanang mo grow ka and teaching on how to struggling mangutana gyud ka, maam unsaon diay ni kay they know na kay labi pag naa ka sa higher grade maam unsay kuan aning bataa ni ngano mani so kabalo sila tanan so ayaw gyud kaulaw nga mangutana sa imong co-teacher nga maam unsa diay ni nga bata ana lang”. (IDI-03)

(Be yourself; do not be shy to ask for help from your fellow because if you are new, just do not be ashamed as long as you grow and ask how to teach a struggling child, like ma'am, how to do this because they know, especially when you are in the higher grade, ma'am, what the problem is with this child. So, they all know, just do not be shy to ask your co-teacher who knows what this child is).

In addition, Sage (pseudonym) expressed the importance of leadership, collaboration, dedication, and the ability to inspire and motivate others. According to her, as a reading coordinator, she is expected to take charge and provide direction to ensure the success of the program. She also highlights the involvement of teachers, the school head, and stakeholders to create a cohesive reading program that benefits the students.

“Reading coordinator need to able to lead and guide the reading program within the school including collaborating with teachers, school head and stalkholder. Finally a genuine fashion for literacy and a dedication to helping students become proficient readers are essential qualities for reading coordinators to inspire and motivate other in the school community”. (IDI-08)

(The reading coordinator needs to lead and guide the reading program within the school, including collaborating with teachers, the school head, and other stakeholders. Finally, a genuine passion for literacy and a dedication to helping students become proficient readers are essential qualities for reading coordinators to inspire and motivate others in the school community).

Moreover, Ally (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of teamwork and community involvement in the education of a child, particularly in the context of a reading program. Ally mentioned that the task of improving literacy among students is not a solitary one, it requires active collaboration and coordination with various stakeholders in the school community.

“As a reading coordinator kailangan jud nimo makig coordinate sa imong co-teachers, school head og other stakeholders like parents kay dili nimo mahimo ang tanan nga ikaw lang dapat naa jud ang community para mo raise sa isa ka bata”. (IDI-09)

(As a reading coordinator, you must coordinate with your co-teachers, school head, and other stakeholders, like parents, because you cannot do all the tasks on your own. It takes a community to raise a child).

Furthermore, Pro (pseudonym) emphasizes the significance of effective communication skills in the educational setting. According to her, communication skills are essential to build rapport with pupils. She also stated that communicating clearly and openly with fellow teachers can foster a commitment to the student’s educational success.

“Effective communication skills are essential for building rapport with our pupils, collaborating with colleagues and partnering with parents clear and open communication ensures that everyone involved in the pupils education is informed and engaged”. (IDI-11)

(Effective communication skills are essential for building rapport with our pupils. Collaborating with colleagues and partnering with parents ensures that everyone involved in their education is informed and engaged).

Lastly, Caring (pseudonym) stresses the significance of partnership between parents, teachers, and students in order to improve the reading levels of the pupils. She believes that involving parents as partners can better the learning experiences of struggling readers.

“Of course we all know that in digging into the reader levels of our pupils we should have the parents as partner, then the teacher and learners need to work together in order to address and to have a better learning especially in their reading.” (IDI-12)

(Of course, we all know that in digging into the reader levels of our pupils we should have the parents as partners, then the teacher and learners need to work together in order to address and to have better learning, especially in their reading).

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers?

This research question focuses on understanding the perspectives and experiences of reading coordinators in handling struggling readers. It aims to gather insights and knowledge from these coordinators to inspire and empower other reading coordinators aspiring to take struggling readers. The question explores the unique perspectives, lessons learned, successes, challenges, and strategies of reading coordinator. By understanding their insights, the research aims to identify key factors that can motivate and empower other reading coordinators to handle a struggling reader.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: patience and empathy in teaching struggling readers, innovative teaching strategies and adaptability in addressing struggling readers, essence of differentiated instruction for diverse learners, and gaining a sense of fulfillment from teaching.

Patience and Empathy in Teaching Struggling Readers

The theme focuses on the importance of patience and empathy in teaching struggling readers. The participants of the study emphasize the need for teachers to continue their efforts, be patient, and maintain a positive attitude towards the learners. It is crucial to have patience and commitment, even when the struggling reader is different from other students. Teachers are encouraged to adopt a motherly figure and a child-friendly approach to encourage struggling readers. Thus, they mentioned that patience, empathy, and a supportive approach are essential for helping struggling readers succeed.

During the interview, Tutor (pseudonym) she believes that with the teacher's guidance and support, the struggling reader will eventually develop the skills and become a reader.

“My advice is continue lang jud no, more patience pajud and be positive that that learner will become a reader in your hand”. (IDI-01)

(My advice is to just continue, be more patient, and be positive that that learner will become a reader in your hands).

As with other participants, Pulse (pseudonym) emphasizes that teachers must have the patience and commitment to help these learners, recognizing that they may require additional time and support to develop their reading skills.

“Dapat pasensya og commitment jud nga kana ganing tinud anay jud na tabangan nimo siya biskan pag ingon ana siya nga klase nga bata, basta dapat kuan jud ka andam”. (IDI-02)

(You must have patience and commitment that you will really help them even though he is different from the other students and be ready as always).

In addition, Mentor (pseudonym) highlights the importance of creating a nurturing and child-friendly environment, while also emphasizing the need for patience and understanding when working with struggling readers.

Table 4. *Insights of Seasoned Reading Coordinators Shares to their Fellow Educators in Handling Struggling Readers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Patience and Empathy in Teaching Struggling Readers	<p>“My advice is to just continue, be more patient, and be positive that that learner will become a reader in your hands.”- IDI- 01</p> <p>You must have patience and commitment so that you will really help him even if he is that kind of child, as long as you are ready.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“As a reading coordinator and classroom teacher, we need to be a motherly figure, have a child-friendly approach to encourage struggling readers, and most of all, have patience with the learners.”-IDI- 03</p> <p>When communicating with struggling readers, we need to be a teacher, we are an adviser, we are reading teachers, we have to be patient and understanding, we encourage the child and we provide positive feedback to your child on those little things, not only in reading. I acknowledge your efforts.”-IDI-10</p> <p>“As a reading teacher, you must have compassion for the children, so that compassion will lead to loving the children you are teaching because they are like, how can we give if we do not have it. So, we must be equipped with the skills in reading.”-IDI-13</p>
Innovative Teaching Strategies and Adaptability in Addressing Struggling Readers	<p>“The effective strategies that I am doing are mentoring by pair sometimes also because we have one-on-one tutoring with the child every afternoon class, and we have catch-up Friday, so this catch-up Friday is more into reading.”-IDI-01</p> <p>“In every grade level, teachers have to use effective strategies like one-on-one, on- one reading, peer reading, group reading, and games, so the teacher will think of making a lot of games so that they can read through games.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“Explicit instruction is that I will share this explanation that is clear to the children. I will also provide direct instruction during my class. I will give an activity that is only intended for their level; you will not give an activity that is not suitable for their level.”- IDI-10</p> <p>“Some specific strategies and tips that can be effective in overcoming the struggles associated with teaching struggling readers are: first, provide individualized support, which tailors instruction to meet each student's specific needs by providing individualized support.”-IDI-11</p> <p>“You should have a diversified reading material because you can create what would be the materials you are using because the root cause is struggling readers, so it's up to you how you are going to address this kind of learner to be a reader, to be a confident one, to be a happy one, a happy individual, and of course, to try to stand up in his or her own way of understanding the process from that simple person in becoming a better one.”-IDI-12</p>
Essence of Differentiated Instruction for Diverse Learners	<p>“In this situation, we are ensuring inclusive learning by giving them differentiated activities, which are easier for the learners who are struggling readers. We are also involving them in the activities inside the classroom.”-IDI-08</p> <p>“In that class, I give different activities to the children based on their level of performance, but they still have the same learning competency as I do because the children are diverse, especially in their abilities and behavior.”-IDI-09</p> <p>“We have differentiated instruction that tailor’s instruction to meet the individual needs and learning styles of each pupil, so we provide a variety of reading materials at different levels of difficulty, including leveled readers, decoded texts, and high- interest books to accommodate diverse learners.”-IDI-11</p> <p>“Actually, they are not neglected or separated; all we need is modified instruction that will suit their capabilities at their reading levels. Therefore, you need to pay more attention to them than give them punishment because they are like this, but you, as a teacher, need to have a strategy in order to address this kind of learner in your class.”-IDI-12</p> <p>“So, you should have a positive mindset because you should know that struggling readers are also diverse learners; their needs and interests are different. You should plan and how you will attack them. How much and how long will you attack them.”-IDI-13</p>
Gaining a Sense of Fulfillment from Teaching	<p>“Accept the challenge because it's for your own professional development and, at the end of the day, fulfilling the sake of seeing your child be able to read.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“Since 2020, I have been the reading coordinator at our school. I have a lot of experience; I have been through many struggling readers, and then I am very happy with the part that I was able to read. Then, every time there is an activity in the school and there are assessments, I am very happy with my part. That your hard work will be paid because you read the child; you just need to get to know the child.”-IDI-10</p> <p>“Actually, reading is difficult because it needs the teacher's capacity to teach, but at the end of the process, there is happiness because you are able to let the child or a certain individual read, even though it is hard to deal with this kind of learner. If this is your fashion, you will be able to see a rainbow after rain because you let this child read on their own level.”- IDI-12</p> <p>“Sometimes it is tiring, but you also enjoy it because you have self-fulfillment, especially posting an assessment that the child has read.”-IDI-13</p> <p>“Just do it with a heart and teach with a heart because once the child feels that your heart is open when you teach him, the child will really work hard. Because I have already been tested and proven and nothing can commensurate the happiness that you can teach the child how to read.”- IDI-14</p>

“As reading coordinator and classroom teacher we need to be a motherly figure and have a child friendly approach to encourage struggling readers and most of all have patient to the learners”. (IDI-03)

(As reading coordinator and classroom teacher we need to be a motherly figure and have a child friendly approach to encourage struggling readers and most of all have patient to the learners).

Moreover, Wisdom (pseudonym) highlights the significance of patience and understanding when communicating with struggling readers. She stated that these learners may face difficulties in reading, but it is crucial not to make them feel inadequate or discouraged. Instead, she focused on the positive aspects of the child's progress, not only in reading but also in other areas.

“When communicating with struggling readers kinahanglan kita teacher, kita adviser, kita reading teacher taas jud tag pasensya then pagsabot and i encourage jud nato ang bata, kanang mo provide jud ka og positive feedback sa imuhang bata kanang mga ginagmay nga butang dili lang sa reading i acknowledge nimo ilahang mga effort”. (IDI-10)

(When communicating with struggling readers, we need to be a teacher, we are an adviser, we are reading teachers, we have to be patient and understanding, and we encourage the child so you provide positive feedback to your child on those little things, not only in reading. I acknowledge your efforts).

Lastly, Wise (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of compassion and love in the role of a reading teacher. She mentioned that having compassion to the learners will leads to love the children. She also implies the need of teachers to be equipped with the necessary skills in reading.

“Reading teacher ka kinahanglan naa jud kay kalooy para sa mga bata so kanang imuhang kalooy that will leads to love the children you are teaching kay ingon sila how can we give if we dont have so dapat kita we are equip with the skills in reading”. (IDI-13)

(As a reading teacher, you must have compassion for the children, so that compassion will lead to loving the children you are teaching because they are like, how can we give if we do not have it. So, we must be equipped with the skills in reading).

Innovative Teaching Strategies and Adaptability in Addressing Struggling Readers

The theme underscores the use of innovative teaching strategies and adaptability in addressing the needs of struggling readers. The participants of the study highlight the implementation of various effective strategies, such as one-on-one tutoring, peer reading, group reading, and games, to engage and support struggling readers. They also emphasize the significance of explicit instruction and providing clear explanations tailored to the student's level.

During the interview, Tutor (pseudonym) highlights the effective strategies implemented to support struggling readers. The participant mentions several strategies, including mentoring by pair, one-on-one tutoring, and catch-up Fridays, which are mandated by higher authorities.

“Akoang effectective na strategies na akong ginabuhat is that katong mentoring by pair usahay pud kay naa mi one on one tutoring sa bata every afternoon class and karon pud kay naa nami catch up Friday so kaning catch up Friday is it is more into reading.” (IDI-01)

(The effective strategies that I am doing are mentoring by pair sometimes also because we have one-on-one tutoring with the child every afternoon class, and we have catch-up Friday, so this catch-up Friday is more into reading).

As with another participant, Mentor (pseudonym) emphasizes the use of effective strategies in every grade level to support reading development. Mentor mentioned that every Friday is designated as a catch-up Friday, following a mandate from the Department of Education. According to her, catch-up Fridays and the emphasis on games as a tool for reading engagement reflect a commitment to creating a positive and enjoyable learning environment. By integrating reading into games and providing opportunities for peer and group reading, the coordinator aims to enhance students' reading skills and foster a love for reading.

“In every grade level teacher have use a effective strategies like ah kanang one on one, one on one reading, peer reading, group reading and game. karong Friday so kung kung makasulod mo sa among rooms more on reading mi pinaagi sa games kay mandated na siya sa deped nga every friday mao na ginatawag nga catch-up friday so si teacher ana thursday palang maghuna-huna nana sila unsa napud akong buhaton pagka ugma sa friday nga ma enjoy ang mga bata kay mao lagi na games so maghuna-huna jud si teacher maghimo jud kag daghan kaayo dula para paagi sa dula ang ilahang pagbasa”. (IDI-03)

(In every grade level, teachers have to use effective strategies like one-on-one, one-on-one reading, peer reading, group reading, and games, so the teacher will think of making a lot of games so that they can read through games.).

In addition, Wisdom (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of explicit instruction and providing clear explanations that are appropriate for the children's level. Aside from that, she highlights the importance of avoiding activities that are too challenging or not suitable for the students' level of development.

“Explicit instruction kanang mag share ko og explanation nga kanang klaro jud sa mga bata, mag provide pud ko anang direct instruction during sa akong klase mag hatag kog activity nga intended lang pud sa ilang level dili ka mohatag og activity nga dili haom sa ilahang level”. (IDI-10)

(Explicit instruction is that I will share an explanation that is clear to the children. I will also provide direct instruction during my class. I will give an activity that is only intended for their level; you will not give an activity that is not suitable for their level).

Moreover, Pro (pseudonym) highlights the importance of individualized support, targeted interventions, and fostering a growth mindset in addressing the struggles of teaching struggling readers. According to her, by implementing these strategies, educators can create a

supportive and empowering learning environment that helps struggling readers overcome their difficulties and develop their reading skills.

“Some specific strategies and tips that can be effective in overcoming the struggles associated with teaching struggling readers are: first, provide individualized support which tailors instruction to meet each student's specific needs by providing individualized support”. (IDI-11)

(Some specific strategies and tips that can be effective in overcoming the struggles associated with teaching struggling readers are: first, provide individualized support, which tailors instruction to meet each student's specific needs by providing individualized support).

Lastly, Caring (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of using diversified reading materials to address the needs of struggling readers. She also suggests that educators have the flexibility to create or select appropriate materials that cater to the specific challenges faced by struggling readers. This insight the role of educators in creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment for struggling readers.

“You should have a diversified reading material because you can create what would be the materials you are using because the root cause is struggling reader so its up to you how you are going to address this kind of learners to be a reader, to be a confident one, to be a happy one, happy individual and of course trying to stand up in his/her own way of understanding on the process from that simple person in becoming a better one”. (IDI-12)

(You should have a diversified reading material because you can create what would be the materials you are using because the root cause is struggling readers, so it's up to you how you are going to address this kind of learner to be a reader, to be a confident one, to be a happy one, a happy individual, and of course, to try to stand up in his or her own way of understanding the process from that simple person in becoming a better one).

Essence of Differentiated Instruction for Diverse Learners

The theme explores the essence of differentiated instruction for diverse learners, specifically focusing on struggling readers. The participants emphasize the importance of tailoring instruction to meet the individual needs and learning styles of each student. They highlight the importance of recognizing and accommodating the unique capabilities and reading levels of these learners. This insight the need for teachers to provide modified instruction and strategies that suit the capabilities of struggling readers, rather than punishing or neglecting them. By giving more attention and implementing effective instructional strategies, educators can support the progress and success of struggling readers in the classroom.

During the interview, Sage (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of inclusive learning and the use of differentiated activities for struggling readers. She mentions that in the given situation, inclusive learning is being ensured by providing differentiated activities specifically designed for learners who are struggling readers. These activities are tailored to be easier and more accessible for these students, taking into consideration their individual needs and challenges.

“In this situation ensuring the inclusive learning by giving them differentiated activity which is mas sayon ang activity sa mga learners nga struggling readers gina involve pud namo na sila sa mga activity inside the classroom”. (IDI-08)

(In this situation, we are ensuring inclusive learning by giving them differentiated activities, which are easier for the learners who are struggling readers. We are also involving them in the activities inside the classroom).

In addition, Ally (pseudonym) highlights the recognition of the diverse abilities and behaviors of students in a particular class. She mentions that different activities are given to the children based on their level of performance, considering their individual capabilities.

“Kanang sa klase lahi lahing activity ang ginahatag nako sa bata based on their level of performance pero pareha gihapon og learning competency ng i meet, kay ang bata man gud diverse na sila labi na sa ilang mga kakayahan og pamatasan”. (IDI-09)

(In that class, I give different activities to the children based on their level of performance, but they still have the same learning competency as I do because the children are diverse, especially in their abilities and behavior).

Moreover, Pro (pseudonym) highlights the implementation of differentiated instruction to meet the individual needs and learning styles of each student. Pro mentions the provision of a variety of reading materials at different levels of difficulty, such as leveled readers, decoded texts, and high-interest books, to accommodate the diverse learners in the classroom.

“We have differentiated instruction which tailor instruction to meet the individual needs and learning styles of each pupil so provide a variety of reading materials at different levels of difficulty including leveled readers, decode texts, and high interest books to accommodate diverse learners”. (IDI-11)

(We have differentiated instruction which tailor instruction to meet the individual needs and learning styles of each pupil so provide a variety of reading materials at different levels of difficulty including leveled readers, decode texts, and high-interest books to accommodate diverse learners).

Furthermore, Caring (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of not neglecting or separating struggling readers but instead providing modified instruction that suits their capabilities and reading levels. The coordinator stresses the need for teachers to give more attention to these learners and avoid punishing them for their difficulties. Instead, the coordinator encourages teachers to develop strategies to effectively address the needs of struggling readers in the classroom.

“Actually they are not neglected or separated just we need is to have a modified instruction that will suit to their capabilities in their reading levels. Therefore you need to have more attention to them rather than giving them a punishment because they are like this no, so you as a teacher you need to have a strategies in order to address this kind of learners in your class”. (IDI-12)

(Actually, they are not neglected or separated just we need is to have modified instruction that will suit their capabilities in their reading levels. Therefore you need to pay more attention to them rather than giving them a punishment because they are like this but you as a teacher need to have a strategy in order to address this kind of learners in your class).

Lastly, Wise (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of having a positive mindset, being emotionally prepared, and planning when working with struggling readers. According to her, this involves recognizing that these learners are also diverse and have different needs and interests. By maintaining a positive mindset, educators can approach the challenges faced by struggling readers with optimism and a belief in their potential for growth and progress.

“So dapat you should have a positive mindset kay you should know that the struggling readers are also diverse learners lahi lahi pud ng ilahang needs og interest, himoan jud na nimo og plano og unsaon nimo sila pag ataki kung pila ka duration nimo sila atakihon kay kung naka plano nana tanan dali nalang para sa imuha unsaon sila pagtudlo”. (IDI-13)

(So, you should have a positive mindset because you should know that struggling readers are also diverse learners; their needs and interests are different, so you should plan how you will attack them. How much and how long will you attack them).

Gaining a Sense of Fulfillment from Teaching

The theme explores the sense of fulfillment that comes from teaching struggling readers and witnessing their progress in reading. The participants share personal experiences and highlights the happiness and fulfillment they feel when a struggling reader is able to read. They also highlight that despite the challenges involved in teaching struggling readers, accepting the challenge is important for professional development and the fulfillment of seeing a child learn to read.

During the interview, Expert (pseudonym) encourages educators to accept the challenge of teaching struggling readers, emphasizing the personal and professional development that comes with it. It also underscores the fulfillment and satisfaction derived from witnessing a child's progress in reading. By accepting this challenge, educators can grow professionally and experience the joy of making a positive impact on a child's learning journey.

“Accept the challenge jud no kay para sa imuha raman gihapon ng professional development at the end of the day fulfilling sa imuha na makita nimong bata nga makabasa”. (IDI-04)

(Accept the challenge because it is for your own professional development and, at the end of the day, fulfilling the sake of seeing your child be able to read).

In addition, Wisdom (pseudonym) highlights her experience and satisfaction in working with struggling readers. She also emphasizes the importance of understanding the individual needs of each child and providing appropriate approaches, materials, and instruction to support their reading development. Her statement reflects the commitment to understand and meet the unique needs of each child, ultimately leading to their growth and success in reading.

“Since 2020 man ata ko naging reading coordinator sa among school daghan kog na experience, daghan kog naagian na struggling readers then happy ko fullfilling kaayo sa akoang part nga nakapabasa ko then every naay activity sa school, naay mga assessment nalipay kaayo ko sa akong part nga kanang ang imong kahago na bayran gud kay nakapabasa man ka sa bata”. (IDI- 10)

(Since 2020, I have been the reading coordinator at our school. I have a lot of experience; I have been through many struggling readers, and then I am very happy with the part that I was able to read. Then, every time there is an activity in the school and there are assessments, I am very happy with my part. That is your hard work that will be paid because you read the child; you just need to get to know the child).

Furthermore, Caring (pseudonym) highlights the challenges and rewards of teaching struggling readers. She mentioned that teaching reading can be difficult and requires the capacity and skills of the teacher. However, despite the challenges, there is a sense of happiness and fulfillment in witnessing a struggling reader or individual learn to read.

“Okay, actually reading is difficult because it needs teacher capacity to teach but at the end of the process there are happiness because you are able to let the child or a certain individual to read but one thing again is its hard to deal with this kind of learners, but if this is your fashion you will able to see a rainbow after a rain because you will able to let this child read in their own level”. (IDI-12)

(Actually, reading is difficult because it needs the teacher's capacity to teach but at the end of the process there is happiness because

you are able to let the child or a certain individual read even though it is hard to deal with this kind of learners, but if this is your fashion you will be able to see a rainbow after a rain because you let this child read on their own level).

Moreover, Wise (pseudonym) shares her experience and insights in working with struggling readers. According to her teaching struggling readers can be tiring at times but also highlights the enjoyment and self-fulfillment that comes with it. The coordinator specifically mentions the satisfaction of posting an assessment indicating that a child has successfully learned to read.

“Usahay kapoy pud baya pero enjoy man pud kay naa kay self fulfillment labi na og pagpost assessment nga nakabasa najud ang bata”. (IDI-13)

(Sometimes it is tiring, but you also enjoy it because you have self-fulfillment, especially posting an assessment that the child has read).

Lastly, Echo (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of teaching with a compassionate and open heart. She stated that when a child feels the teacher's genuine care and openness, they are more motivated to work hard and succeed.

“Kuan lang jud ka doing with a heart and teaching with a heart kay once ma feel niya nga ubad imong kasing kasing sa imong pagtudlo sa iyaha maningkamot the more maningkamot ang bata, kuan najud na maam tested and proven najud na nako so walay ikatugbang ang kalipay nga makapabasa gani ka sa bata”. (IDI-14)

(Just do it with a heart and teach with a heart because once the child feels that your heart is open when you teach him, the child will really work hard. Because I have already been tested and proven and nothing can commensurate the happiness that you can teach the child how to read).

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study has shed light on the experiences of seasoned reading in handling struggling readers within public elementary schools. Through thematic analysis, key insights have emerged regarding the strategies, challenges, and benefits associated with teaching struggling readers.

As I reflect on my research journey, I am struck by the dedication and commitment demonstrated by seasoned reading coordinators in handling struggling readers. Their unwavering support, coupled with their passion for teaching, has been instrumental in shaping learnings of the struggling readers.

Moreover, this study underscores the importance of teaching struggling readers and highlights the significant role that seasoned reading coordinators play in supporting the growth and development of struggling readers. It is fundamental that we continue to teach a struggling reader, providing resources, support, and professional development opportunities for seasoned coordinators to enhance their teaching process. By doing so, we can ensure struggling readers receive the guidance and support they need to thrive in the classroom and make a positive impact on student learning.

As I conclude this research journey, I am inspired by the potential for reading coordinators to transform student's education and contribute to the ongoing improvement of student's progress. Reading coordinators hold a unique role in fostering not only literacy skills but also a foundation for lifelong learning. By implementing targeted reading strategies, evaluating individual student needs, and collaborating with teachers, they can customize reading instruction to suit a wide range of abilities and backgrounds. Their efforts ensure that reading interventions go beyond responding to immediate challenges, proactively cultivating essential skills that contribute to students' overall success across subjects. This role extends beyond instruction it represents the transformative potential of education, making learning more accessible and achievable for all students.

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